

Utility of Pleural Fluid ADA/Serum CRP Ratio in Differentiating Tubercular Pleural Effusion and Parapneumonic Pleural EffusionJia Ur Rahman¹, Farjana Begum², Basanta Hazarika³, Manash Jyoti Saikia⁴¹Postgraduate Trainee, Dept. of Pulmonary Medicine, Gauhati Medical College Hospital²Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pulmonary Medicine, Gauhati Medical College Hospital³Professor & HOD, Dept. of Pulmonary Medicine, Gauhati Medical College Hospital⁴Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pulmonary Medicine, Gauhati Medical College Hospital

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Objectives: Tubercular pleural effusion (TPE) and Parapneumonic pleural effusion (PPE) are usually distinguished by cellular predominance and pleural fluid adenosine deaminase (ADA) levels. However, both diseases may occasionally show similar cellular predominance and moderate or high ADA levels. In such cases, differential diagnosis between TPE and PPE is challenging. Our objective is to assess the role of Pleural fluid ADA/Serum CRP ratio in differentiating TPE and PPE.

Methods: This Hospital based Retrospective Case Control Study is conducted on TPE and PPE patients. A total of 36 patients were included in the study, comprising 16 TPE patients and 20 PPE patients. Patient demographics and laboratory data were collected through a retrospective review of both groups and compared. The pleural fluid ADA to serum CRP (C - reactive protein) ratio was calculated. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves were constructed for identifying TPE.

Results: Pleural fluid ADA/S-CRP ratio provided diagnostic accuracy with an area under the ROC curve of 0.78. At a cutoff value of 3.2 ADA/S-CRP ratio had a sensitivity of 75%, specificity of 85%, positive likelihood ratio of 5, and negative likelihood ratio 0.29.

Conclusion: Pleural fluid ADA/S-CRP ratio, a simple method using routine laboratory tests, may be helpful in discriminating between TPE and PPE patients.

Keywords: Tubercular pleural effusion (TPE), Parapneumonic effusion (PPE), Adenosine deaminase (ADA), C-reactive protein (CRP).

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Introduction

Pleural Effusion is abnormal and excessive fluid accumulation in pleural space. It is differentiated into Transudative and exudative pleural effusion using Lights Criteria [1]. Tubercular pleural effusion (TPE) and parapneumonic pleural effusion (PPE) are common causes of exudative pleural effusion [2]. They are usually distinguished by cellular predominance and pleural fluid adenosine deaminase (ADA) levels [3].

However, both diseases may occasionally show similar cellular predominance and moderate or high ADA levels [4,5]. Rapid microbiologic tests of pleural fluid, such as an acid-fast bacilli smear, Nucleic acid amplification test, gram stain or culture are usually negative [6]. In such cases, differential diagnosis between TPE and PPE is challenging.

Systemic inflammatory response of patients with PPE is generally greater than that of patients with

TPE [7]. Serum C Reactive Protein (S-CRP) was discovered in 1930 and widely used as a sensitive marker but a nonspecific marker of systemic inflammation. Increase in the serum CRP levels is seen in many pulmonary diseases such as pneumonia, malignancies, pulmonary thrombo-embolism. S-CRP is a protein of acute phase inflammation that is produced by liver.

CRP has the ability to recognize the pathogens and to eliminate them through the recruitment of the phagocytic cells and the complement system. Complicated PPE shows higher S-CRP levels and pleural fluid ADA in comparison to uncomplicated PPE [8,9]. It may be more helpful to examine relationships between each disease and the systemic inflammatory response.

The Aim and Objective of this study is to estimate the utility of Pleural fluid ADA/Serum CRP ratio in differentiating TPE and PPE.

Materials and Methods

This Hospital based Retrospective Case Control Study was conducted during January 2023 to July 2023, in the department of Pulmonary Medicine, Gauhati Medical College Hospital. Ethical committee approval was taken from the Gauhati Medical College Ethical Committee.

All patients diagnosed with Tubercular Pleural Effusion and Parapneumonic Effusion during the specified period was reviewed retrospectively. Patients who met the following criteria were included in the study.

The study included TPE patients over 18 years old who were diagnosed through thoracoscopic biopsy, pleural fluid NAAT, sputum AFB smear or NAAT, and BAL AFB smear or NAAT. The control group consisted of PPE patients characterized by exudative effusion associated with bacterial pneumonia, lung abscess, or bronchiectasis, with no evidence of Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB) in pleural fluid, sputum, or BAL.

Methodology

The study included a total of 36 patients, comprising 16 TPE patients and 20 PPE patients based on the specified inclusion and exclusion criteria. Patient demographics and laboratory data were collected through a retrospective review of both groups.

Blood investigation and pleural fluid profiles performed in the same day were analysed. Variables were expressed as the median (interquartile range [IQR]) and differences between groups were analysed using the Mann–Whitney U test. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves were constructed for identifying TPE.

Optimal cutoff values for the prediction of TPE were selected using the ROC curve analysis and the diagnostic accuracy was assessed from the area under the curve (AUC).

Results

A total of 36 patients were included in the study where 16 (44%) were Tubercular effusion and 20 were parapneumonic effusion (56%) cases. (Table 1, Fig- 1)

Table 1: Types of Pleural effusion in study population

Group	Number of patients	Percentage (%)
Tubercular Pleural effusion	16	44%
Parapneumonic effusion	20	56%

Figure 1: Types of pleural effusion in study population

Out of 16 tubercular effusion cases, 11 were males and 5 were females. And out of 20 parapneumonic effusion cases, 12 were males. (Fig 2)

Table 2: Gender Distribution in the study population

Gender	Male	Female
TPE	11	5
PPE	12	8

Figure 2: Gender Distribution in the study population

Sixteen tubercular effusions were diagnosed by Thoracoscopic Biopsy (n=6), pleural fluid NAAT (n=2), sputum AFB Smear or NAAT (n=3), BAL AFB Smear or NAAT (n= 5). (Fig 3)

Table 3: Methods of Diagnosis of tubercular pleural effusion

Method of Diagnosis	No. of patients	Percentage
Thoracoscopic Biopsy	6	37%
Pleural fluid NAAT	2	13%
Sputum AFB smear/NAAT	3	19%
BAL AFB smear/ NAAT	5	31%

Figure 3: Methods of Diagnosis of tubercular pleural effusion

Twenty PPE patients met the inclusion criteria and were included as a control group. In these 20 PPE patients, specific bacterial pathogens were identified in 6 (30 %) patients. The remaining 14 (70 %) PPE patients showed a clinical and radiological response to antibiotics and had no other cause for at least 3 months at follow-up. They exhibited no evidence of MTB in the cultures of serial pleural fluid, sputum, or BAL.

Pleural Fluid and blood Parameters

In the study, both types of effusions were exudative. The mean pleural fluid protein levels were 4.8 mg/dl in tubercular pleural effusion and 4.2 mg/dl in parapneumonic effusion.

The concentrations of pleural fluid protein and glucose did not differ significantly between the two groups.

Table 4: Pleural fluid parameters in the study population

Mean Pleural fluid parameters	Tubercular pleural Effusion	Parapneumonic Effusion
Protein	4.8mg/dL	4.2mg/dL
Sugar	86 mg/dL	71 mg/dL
Total count	624/uL	1200/uL
Lymphocytes	80%	40%

The median values of pleural fluid ADA levels in patients with TPE and PPE were 53.0 and 14.5 U/L, respectively, and were significantly different between the two groups ($p < 0.001$). The serum CRP level in PPE patients was higher than TPE;

however, the difference was not statistically significant. The median pleural fluid ADA to serum CRP ratio was significantly higher in TPE patients compared to PPE patients, with values of 3.6 for TPE and 0.9 for PPE ($p < 0.001$)

Table 5: Comparing Pleural fluid ADA, serum CRP and ADA/S.CRP ratio in the study population IQR= Interquartile Range, N= sample size, SD= standard deviation

Parameters	Group	N	Mean	SD	Median (IQR)	p value
ADA	PPE	20	16.15	9.12	14.5(10-20.3)	<0.001
	TPE	16	58.25	37.33	53.0(30.5-80.5)	
CRP	PPE	20	42.6	49.5	21.7(8.1-43.8)	0.621
	TPE	16	28.1	30.86	15.5(8.3-43.8)	
ADA/S.CRP	PPE	20	1.32	1.40	0.9 (0.2-1.8)	<0.001
RATIO	TPE	16	3.36	1.89	3.6(1.9-3.7)	

In the ROC curve analysis, the pleural fluid ADA/S-CRP ratio had AUC of 0.78. At a cutoff value of 3.2 ADA/S-CRP ratio had a sensitivity of 75%, specificity of 85%, positive likelihood ratio of 5, and negative likelihood ratio 0.29. (Fig- 4)

Figure 4: Receiver operating characteristics (ROC) curve of serum C-reactive protein (S-CRP), pleural fluid adenosine deaminase (ADA) and pleural fluid ADA/S-CRP ratio.

In the study, 12 out of 16 (75%) tubercular effusions exceeded the cut-off value of 3.2 as determined by the ROC curve, while 4 tubercular effusions did not. In the parapneumonic effusion group, only 3 out of 20 (15%) effusions surpassed the cut-off value, whereas 17 out of 20 did not. (Figure- 5)

Figure 5: Distribution of pleural fluid adenosine deaminase (ADA)/serum C-reactive protein (S-CRP) ratio in patients with tuberculous pleural effusion (TPE) and parapneumonic effusion (PPE)

Discussion

This study shows the improved diagnostic performance of the pleural fluid ADA/S-CRP ratio in the differentiation between TPE and PPE. In this study, we found that at a cutoff value of 3.2 ADA/S-CRP ratio had a sensitivity of 75%, specificity of 85%.

Findings of this study are comparable to the findings of the study done by Jaehee Lee et al [9], where at a cutoff value of 5.62, ADA/S-CRP ratio had a sensitivity of 89%, specificity of 88% for diagnosing TPE. It is a simple, rapid, and objective method that utilizes the biomarkers routinely assessed in clinical practice. Advanced forms of PPE frequently exceed the ADA cutoff value for TPE. Higher pleural fluid ADA levels were associated with a greater chance of TPE, while most PPE showed pleural fluid ADA levels below 40 U/L or distributed around 40 U/L.[5,8] S-CRP levels are comparatively less in TPE patients than PPE patients.[7].

Systemic inflammatory markers or pleural fluid profiles alone provided less diagnostic performance than parameters combined by both systemic inflammatory markers and pleural fluid profiles (ADA/S-CRP). These findings suggest that the respective systemic and pleural responses may be independent and the combination of these independent characteristics can maximize the ability to discriminate between the two diseases.

Limitations

It was a Retrospective study. Only routine biomarkers of blood and pleural fluid were included in this study. The sample size was small. This study was only performed in patients diagnosed with TPE and PPE. Pleural effusions with other causes may have neutrophilic predominance and high pleural fluid ADA levels, such as connective tissue diseases [10]. Thus, our results were limited to patients with TPE and PPE.

Conclusion

This study provides a simple parameter may be helpful in discriminating between TPE and PPE patients especially in patients having moderate to high pleural fluid ADA using the available routine laboratory tests. This simple, rapid, and objective predictor may be useful in early clinical decisions and the management of these patients.

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